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Research Article

ANALYSIS OF DEPRESSION, ANXIETY AND ITS RELATED RISK FACTORS IN PATIENTS WITH LUMBER DISC HERNIATION¹Dr Rameen Masood, ²Dr Lubna Mahek, ³Dr Hafiz Muhammad Umer Mehran¹Services Hospital, Lahore.²Mayo hospital, Lahore.³Lahore general hospital, Lahore

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Abstract:

Introduction: Low back pain (LBP), as one of the most common diseases, is being experienced by about 70% of people at some point in their life. **Objectives of the study:** The main objective of the study is to analyse the depression, anxiety and its related risk factors in patients with lumbar disc herniation. **Methodology of the study:** This cross sectional study was conducted in Services hospital Lahore during October 2018 to January 2019. The data was collected from 100 patients who were suffering from lumbar disc herniation. The data of depression and anxiety was collected through a questionnaire which were designed according to depression and anxiety scale. **Results:** The data was collected from 100 lumbar disc herniation patients. There were 20 females and 30 males. The mean age of the participants was 58.8 ± 5.46 years and the mean GAD-7 score was 5.0. Almost 50% of the patients were suffering from chronic pain prior to surgery, which was defined as pain lasting for at least 6 months. The mean pain score was high before the surgery as compared to post surgery period. Mean NRS scores preoperatively were 6.8 (SD 2.6), and decreased to 2.9 (SD 2.4) 6-weeks after surgery. **Conclusion:** It is concluded that lumbar disc herniation conscripts have some psychological problems, such as depression and anxiety, in comparison with healthy controls.

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INTRODUCTION:

Low back pain (LBP), as one of the most common diseases, is being experienced by about 70% of people at some point in their life. It affects the quality of life in patients, and imposes a high economic burden on social health care system. Moreover, LBP is associated with psychological disturbance including depression and anxiety, which influence the outcomes of treatment adversely [1]. Degenerative disc disease is commonly accounted as causal in acute and chronic back/leg pain in the general population. About 15% of patients with a herniated disc require surgery, because they do not respond to conservative approaches or experience major neurologic losses. The main function of surgical treatment is the elimination of pain and associated physical dysfunction. Therefore, the measuring of pain is an important indicator for surgical success [2].

Studies showed that surgery helps the majority of patients to overcome pain symptoms, but between 7 and 23% of the operated patients still report severe pain or even experience no pain relief at all [3]. While surgical complications may be responsible for persisting symptoms in some patients, these problems do not give an all-embracing explanation for ongoing pain. Whether a patient benefits sufficiently from surgery or not can most likely be explained by patient characteristics [4]. Research revealed different socio-demographic, medical, occupational and psychological factors that were associated with persistent pain.

Lumbar disc herniation (LDH) is one of the most important causes of low back pain in adulthood. LDH patients may be usually treated with conservative care and a nonsurgical approach, such as physical therapy and pharmacotherapy for pain relief [5]. Only 1% of these patients have a medical

condition requiring surgical intervention. One of the most important clinical variables to determine surgical approaches to LDH patients is the severity of pain and disability [6].

Objectives of the study

The main objective of the study is to analyse the depression, anxiety and its related risk factors in patients with lumbar disc herniation.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY:

This cross sectional study was conducted in Services hospital Lahore during October 2018 to January 2019. The data was collected from 100 patients who were suffering from lumbar disc herniation. The data of depression and anxiety was collected through a questionnaire which were designed according to depression and anxiety scale. Anxiety was assessed with the Generalized Anxiety Disorder 7-Item Scale GAD-7. Preoperative pain duration for more than 6 months was defined as chronic pain as specified in the German pain questionnaire.

Statistical analysis

All the collected data was entered into SPSS version 21.0 for further analysis. All the values were expressed in mean and standard deviation.

RESULTS:

The data was collected from 100 lumbar disc herniation patients. There were 20 females and 30 males. The mean age of the participants was 58.8 ± 5.46 years and the mean GAD-7 score was 5.0. Almost 50% of the patients were suffering from chronic pain prior to surgery, which was defined as pain lasting for at least 6 months. The mean pain score was high before the surgery as compared to post surgery period. Mean NRS scores preoperatively were 6.8 (SD 2.6), and decreased to 2.9 (SD 2.4) 6-weeks after surgery.

Table 01: Socio-demographic data and pain score of 50 participants

Characteristics	N=100
Mean age (standard deviation)	58.8±5.46
95% confidence interval of age	55.7–62.0
Range of age	24.4–86.9
Educational level	
Mean preoperative anxiety (standard deviation)	5.0±3.76
Number of anxiety cases ^c (N, %)	45 (42.5)
Mild anxiety (GAD-7 score 6–9)	33.0%
Moderate anxiety (GAD-7 score 10–14)	6.6%
Severe anxiety (GAD-7 score >=15)	2.8%
Mean body mass index (standard deviation)	27.9±4.54
Preoperative ASA (American Society of Anesthesiologists physical status classification system)	
ASA 1 (%)	9 (8.5)
ASA 2 (%)	51 (48.1)
ASA 3 (%)	45 (42.5)
ASA 4 (%)	1 (0.9)
Mean duration of surgery in minutes (standard deviation)	117 (53)

95% confidence interval of duration of surgery	107–127
Range of duration of surgery	40–299

DISCUSSION:

Back pain is a common and frequently occurring disease with complicated clinical etiology, which is mainly related to people's bad living habits, such as long-term head bending posture. It is easy to relapse and lasts for a long time [7]. Long-term chronic pain has a profound impact on patients' mental health, and they are prone to negative emotions such as anxiety and depression, which seriously affect patients' quality of life. Reportedly, the longer the chronic pain lasts, the more severe it becomes and the more anxious or depressive it becomes [8]. Meanwhile, anxiety and depression can also promote psychological responses to chronic pain. Among socio-demographic variables, BMI, but not age or sex, was also predictive for ongoing pain 6-months after lumbar disc surgery, but not for the intake of analgesics. Anxiety, assessed with the GAD-7 questionnaire, had no predictive value, neither for pain nor for analgesic consumption [9]. The role of psychological factors such as anxiety, depression or catastrophizing for the outcome of patients undergoing herniated disc surgery is considered as relevant, as shown in several review articles. In a systematic review using different measures for preoperative anxiety and catastrophizing, these psychological factors were shown to play a role in the development of chronic postsurgical pain [10].

Disability is a good clinical assessment of severity in low back pain, and is also a determinant of returning to work, and is related to the transition from acute episode to chronicity in patients with low back pain [11]. Previous studies suggested that some psychological factors such as depression (or distress) and anxiety (or fear avoidance) are the significant predictors of functional disability in patients with low back pain.

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that lumbar disc herniation conscripts have some psychological problems, such as depression and anxiety, in comparison with healthy controls. Depression and anxiety were significantly associated with functional disability, but state anxiety, not depression, predicted functional disability of the LDH conscripts.

REFERENCES:

1. Laufenberg-Feldmann R, Kappis B. Assessing preoperative anxiety using a questionnaire and

clinical rating: a prospective observational study. *Eur J Anaesthesiol.* 2013;30:758–763

2. Hegarty D, Shorten G. Multivariate prognostic modeling of persistent pain following lumbar discectomy. *Pain Physician.* 2012;15:421–434.
3. Lowe B, Decker O, Muller S, Brahler E, Schellberg D, Herzog W, Herzberg PY. Validation and standardization of the generalized anxiety disorder screener (GAD-7) in the general population. *Med Care.* 2008;46:266–274.
4. Nagel B, Gerbershagen HU, Lindena G, Pflingsten M. Development and evaluation of the multidimensional German pain questionnaire. *Schmerz.* 2002;16:263–270
5. Stubhaug A, Breivik H. Prevention and treatment of hyperalgesia and persistent pain after surgery. In: Breivik H, Shipley M, editors. *Pain best practice and research compendium.* London: Elsevier; 2007. pp. 281–288.
6. Breivik H, Borchgrevink PC, Allen SM, Rosseland LA, Romundstad L, Hals EK, Kvarstein G, Stubhaug A. Assessment of pain. *Br J Anaesth.* 2008;101:17–24
7. Spitzer RL, Kroenke K, Williams JB, Lowe B. A brief measure for assessing generalized anxiety disorder: the GAD-7. *Arch Intern Med.* 2006;166:1092–1097.
8. Gugliotta M, da Costa BR, Dabis E, Theiler R, Juni P, Reichenbach S, Landolt H, Hasler P. Surgical versus conservative treatment for lumbar disc herniation: a prospective cohort study. *BMJ Open.* 2016;6:e012938.
9. Junge A, Dvorak J, Ahrens S. Predictors of bad and good outcomes of lumbar disc surgery. A prospective clinical study with recommendations for screening to avoid bad outcomes. *Spine (Phila Pa 1976)* 1995;20:460–468.
10. Zieger M, Schwarz R, König HH, Härter M, Riedel-Heller SG. Depression and anxiety in patients undergoing herniated disc surgery: relevant but Underresearched – a systematic review. *Cen Eur Neurosurg.* 2010;71:26–34.
11. Dorow M, Lobner M, Stein J, Konnopka A, Meisel HJ, Gunther L, Meixensberger J, Stengler K, König HH, Riedel-Heller SG. Risk factors for postoperative pain intensity in patients undergoing lumbar disc surgery: a systematic review. *PLoS One.* 2017;12:e0170303.